

ISic0082

I.Sicily inscription 0082

Language

Latin

Type

terminus

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)**Place of origin (modern)**

Castronuovo di Sicilia

Provenance

Cassero-Colonne de Castronovo, summit of hill S. Vitale de Kassar, seen already in 1939

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Antonino Salinas, inventory 26995

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height 40 cm

Width 40 cm

Depth 22 cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line

1
: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to

2
: mm

Text

1. M (assa) Pician (ensis)

2. [P]etri bac (u) l (um) .

Apparatus

Text of Bivona 1995

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491383

EDCS 3000421

Bibliography

1888-. L'année épigraphique: revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine.. *L'année épigraphique : revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine..* At 1996.0811

Bivona, L. 1997-1998. Epigrafia Latina. *Kokalos*. 43-44: 613-624. At 614

Bivona, L. 1995. Su un iscrizione da Castronuovo (Palermo). *Kokalos*. 41: 23-28.

Giustolisi, V. 1999. Petra: atlante delle antiche strutture rupestri dell'alta valle del Platani (Castronovo). Palermo. At 17

Licensed under a Creative
Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-17): ISic0082. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4334059>